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Designing Feedback Using 360-Degree Feedback for Era Ascot

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to provide feedback using 360-Degree Feedback for each position in the Era Ascot. Era Ascot is a property brokerage company engaged in property agent services. Due to the company being engaged in property agent services, agents (marketing associates) are a critical aspect of the company's survival. Therefore, to produce high-quality agents, one of the methods that can be done is to provide feedback on performance as evaluation and development material. In this study, the researcher used a case study method. The data collection techniques used were interviews and literature studies. The type of research used is descriptive analysis with a qualitative approach. This research results in the application design of 360-degree feedback in providing feedback presented in the assessment form. This form consists of setting objectives, assessment instruments, number of assessor sources, rating scale, period, assessment form, assessment standards, feedback provider, and feedback period. The assessment instrument used in this study was competency. Competencies are designed based on derivative vision and mission, competency architecture, competency dictionary, and competency profile. Produce core competencies and managerial competencies. The suggestions filed by the researcher for Era Ascot are to do some socialization about the 360-degree feedback method, conduct trials, and evaluate the process of providing feedback using 360-degree feedback

Keywords

Feedback, 360-Degree Feedback, Competencies

Introduction

In Indonesia, one type of service that proliferated after the current housing and property industry was formed is property brokerage services. A property broker is an intermediary from the property owner (investor/developer) to a group of consumers who market, provide property consultancy services, and ensure property maintenance. Furthermore, they also provide property investment consulting services, maintenance, and other similar services. Property brokers provide all these services to ensure sales, purchase,

rental/contract agreements, exchanges, and cooperation agreements happen. (Minister of Trade of the Republic of Indonesia, 2015).

According to (AREBI, 2020) data, there are 1,119 companies registered as members of the Indonesian Real Estate Brokers Association (AREBI) spread throughout Indonesia. According to (Rafitas, 2005), in a professional property agent, there are implementing elements that run the property business, namely: i) Principal/member broker, as the owner of the agency who has a responsibility to stakeholders in royalty payments according to the agreement; ii) Marketing Executive/Marketing associate/Property Consultant, as the party running the property brokerage business and; iii) Marketing manager/Property manager, the party appointed by the principal in supervising the course of business activities.

A broker's performance is measured by the number of sales they make. Brokers work in teams and deal directly with customers. Brokers need positive or negative feedback on their performance to improve their capabilities. However, feedback is generally used in training and development rather than performance appraisal and improvement approaches. One of the feedback systems used is *360-degree feedback* (Rivai, 2005, p. 3). The *360-Degree Feedback process* by (Lepsinger & Lucia, *The Art and Science of 360-Degree Feedback*, 2009, p. 11) is considered to provide information about each individual's skills, knowledge, and style that it is the reason for many companies to implement this system, with Era Ascot being one of them.

Era Ascot is a franchise company from Era Indonesia located in Medan City. Operating since March 24, 2019, until now, Era Ascot already has 53 marketing associates with a partnership system and applies a 360-degree feedback system on an ongoing basis to its brokers. Systematic feedback is carried out to be an evaluation material and benchmark for realizing company values, including attitude, commitment, skill, and knowledge. Era Ascot does not yet have a standard measurement system in providing feedback. Thus, the feedback obtained may be biased and less objective. Based on this phenomenon, the author wants to analyze the application of the 360-degree feedback method in providing feedback to marketing associates in the Ascot Era. This method can be a standard and systematic assessment tool so that the feedback received is valid and objective.

Literature Review

Human Resource Management Theory

Human resource management is a series of activities that enable workers and employers' organizations to agree on the nature, goals related to work, and ways to fulfill these agreements (Torrington, Hall, & Taylor, 2008, p. 25). Human resource management is a strategic and coherent approach to human management as

an organization's most valuable asset that works individually and collectively to contribute to achieving its goals (Amstrong, 2006, p. 3). More technically, according to (Hariandja, 2002, pp. 3-4), human resource management aims to discuss employee productivity, reducing absenteeism, reducing employee turnover, and increasing employee loyalty to the organization. In achieving the goals of human resource management, efforts are being made to achieve these goals. According to (Hariandja, 2002, pp. 4-6), there are four crucial human resource management activities as follows: a) Preparation and Procurement, aiming to find out job descriptions, job specifications, and job performance standards in each position in the organization; b) Development and Assessment, This activity is needed to help each employee's career planning and as an employee development effort; c) Compensation and Protection, maintaining the morale and motivation of the organization generally providing compensation or other welfare benefits; d) Employment Relations, the organization and trade unions must synergize in order to achieve the right organizational goals.

Performance Management

Performance management identifies, measures, and develops individual and team performance and aligns performance with the organization's strategic goals, which has two critical components: a continuous process and aligned strategic objectives (Aguinis, 2012, p. 3). In line with this understanding, (Amstrong, 1994, p. 29) states that performance management is the process of understanding and managing performance within a framework of goals, standards, and requirements for attributes/competencies that have been agreed upon to get good results from organizations, teams, and individuals. (Aguinis, 2012) explains that performance management is a continuous process because it has six (6) interrelated components (performance management processes) including: i) Prerequisite, is the first activity in performance management that has two essential requirements regarding knowledge about the mission and organizational goals and knowledge of the work to achieve organizational goals; ii) Performance Planning, requires employees to understand the performance management system as an organizational responsibility including consideration of results, behavior, and development; iii) Performance Execution, including employee commitment in achieving goals, continuous feedback, and coaching, communication with supervisors, collecting and sharing performance data, and preparing performance reviews; iv) Performance Assessment, Employees and supervisors must be able to evaluate performance. Employee involvement in performance appraisals will provide vital information during performance review discussions; v) Performance Review, involves a meeting between employees and managers to review their assessment. Effectively providing feedback is very important because it leads to increased performance and employee satisfaction with the system; vi) Performance Renewal & Recontracting, the stage of performance planning by using the information collected during the review period to make adjustments needs.

Performance Feedback

According to (Amstrong, 1994, p. 186), feedback is one of the positive performance management activities which shows ways for further development and improvement. Feedback is factual, referring to significant outcomes, events, incidents, and significant behaviours. In line with (Hart, 2011, p. 10) asserts that feedback is essential assessment data that supports a specific way to target the desired change in a person. (Aguinis, 2012) argues that feedback has several benefits in facilitating the desired development of the organization, namely: a) Building an employee's confidence in his performance; b) Developing employee competencies through clear communication on performance evaluation as evaluation material as well; c) Increase engagement by receiving and discussing performance to create an understanding of the vital role of employees in the organization. According to (Garber, 2004, pp. 61-64), there are several levels of feedback, each of which will create a different system, namely: i) No Feedback, a situation without implementing a feedback system; ii) No Formal Feedback/Documentation, means that there is no standard system such as standard formulas or notes on performance appraisal feedback; iii) Formal Feedback System, applying feedback using a quantitative approach through a rating scale; iv) Formal Feedback System – Personalized Communication, in this level using a format by combining numerical or quantitative performance measures with personalized feedback; v) Formal Feedback System – Multi-Source, this level focuses on taking feedback information from many sources (multi-source). This gives individuals several different perspectives; vi) Self-Directed Feedback, this level, believes that a person has a different tolerance for feedback. The focus in this approach starts from the point of view or perspective of the recipient of the feedback.

360-Degree Feedback Theory

360-Degree feedback is a systematic collection of performance data and will provide feedback to individuals or groups from several stakeholders on their performance. Generally, data is fed back in ratings against various performance dimensions. 360-Degree feedback is also often referred to as multi-source feedback, where the source of feedback is obtained from direct subordinates, direct superiors, co-workers, and internal customers (Amstrong, Performance Management, 1994, p. 158). By increasing the number of evaluations to stabilize and broaden the view of performance appraisals, 360-degree feedback exists to improve the quality of performance calculations. Because the feedback provides an assessment of how employees typically interact daily, work is reliable, valid, and trustworthy. The following is the difference between the 360-degree feedback method and the traditional single-source:

Figure 1 Single-Source VS Multi-Source Feedback

(Edwards & Ewen, 1996, p. 5)

According to (Lepsinger & Lucia, *The Art and Science of 360-Degree Feedback*, 2009, pp. 8-11), the 360-Degree Feedback process is used to gather information about an individual's skills, knowledge, and style. This is an essential element of professional development, learning, and receiving negative feedback. In addition, according to (Rao & Raju, 2014), 360-degree feedback or multi-source feedback is an excellent tool to increase the effectiveness of individuals, managers, and leaders wherever they are. By using 360-degree feedback assessors, employees get feedback from various sources on their behavior or competence, such as how they should do a job, their behavior, and the results of what they do. In addition, 360 degrees can also provide comprehensive and diverse benefits to stakeholders such as customers, employees, team members, supervisors, leaders and managers, and organizations.

Data Collection Technique

In this study, the author used primary and secondary data. Primary data is data collected by researchers from primary sources where the data did not exist before (Juliandi, Irfan, & Manurung, 2014, p. 65). Primary data will be collected through interviews. An interview is a data collection activity by conducting guided and directed conversations between two or more people (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016, p. 113). In this case, the author interviewed the CEO of Era Ascot to collect company issues related to human resources, data regarding the company's vision and mission, and organizational structure. Secondary data is data collected by researchers from other available sources by quoting from existing studies for research purposes (Juliandi, Irfan, & Manurung, 2014, p. 66). Secondary data will be collected using a literature study.

Population

The population is a whole from an area consisting of objects or subjects with specific qualities and characteristics that are the subject of research and are studied and then drawn conclusions (Sugiyono, 2015, p. 80). The population consists of a group of people, events, or things studied by researchers (Sekaran &

Bougie, 2016, p. 236). This study, which includes the population, is a feedback system for all marketing associates, CEOs, and leaders of each group in Era Ascot Medan.

Data Analysis Techniques

The data analysis technique used by the author is qualitative data analysis. Qualitative data analysis is data analysis carried out from the beginning to the location of data collection, which can be done by getting as much information as saving, namely reducing, grouping, and others to produce interpretations (Hamidi, 2004, p. 16). The interpretation of the data in question is that carried out by research through checking and agreement with the research subject.

Research Framework

The research framework used refers to the stages of 360 Degree Feedback, including:

- Determination of research objectives elaborated with supporting theories
- Determination of assessment instruments
- Number of appraisal sources
- Scoring scale
- Making 360 Degree Feedback Questionnaire
- Assessment standards as the basis for providing feedback
- Feedback period

Analysis

This study aims to design a process of giving feedback using *360-degree feedback*, where this design uses *360-degree feedback* stages. In addition, to support the design that will be carried out, researchers also refer to supporting theories and data obtained in the field. The stages of *360-degree feedback* will be explained further below :

Corporate Competency Development

Compilation of Competency Architecture

This stage refers to a review conducted on the organization through an interview process with the founder of Era Ascot. Based on the interviews, the author obtained data such as the company's vision, mission, business goals, organizational structure, and job descriptions. The data obtained will be used to reduce the vision and mission of Era Ascot. In addition to the data obtained from the company, the researcher also matched the Decree of the Minister of Manpower of the Republic of Indonesia No. 343 of 2015 concerning the Stipulation of Indonesian National Work Competency Standards for Real Estate Categories of Real Estate Main Classes in the Property Trade Intermediary Sector. The following is a summary of the competencies possessed by Era Ascot:

Figure 2 Era Ascot Competency Architecture

Competence : Compilation of Competency Dictionaries

Competence	Home Financing Knowledge
Definition	The ability to understand property financing and elements of property transactions, such as building loans and taxes.

Level	Behavior Indicator
1	- Understand the types of home financing and how to use them
2	- Understand the types of home financing and how to use them - Understand the types of home financing and how to use them. - Has the knowledge to maximize the funding function in conducting transactions.
3	- Comprehend the types of home financing and how to use them. - Has the knowledge to maximize the funding function in conducting transactions. - Create a home financing strategy that will to give to each customer for profitable transactions.
4	- Understand the types of home financing and how to use them. - Has the knowledge to maximize the funding function in conducting transactions. - Create a home financing strategy to give to each customer for profitable transactions - Take a role in home financing partnerships with banks/financial companies.

Job Competency Profile

Competency Aspect	Position
--------------------------	-----------------

		Operational				
		Director (D)	Manager (M)	Office Coordinator (OC)	Team Leader (TL)	Marketing Associate (MA)
No	General Competence					
1	Property Knowledge	4	3	2	2	1
2	Home Financing Knowledge	4	3	2	2	1
3	Marketing Knowledge	4	3	-	2	1
4	Communication	4	3	1	2	1
5	Relationship Management	4	3	-	2	1
6	Negotiation	4	3	-	2	1
7	Technology Capability	4	3	1	2	1
8	Professional	4	3	1	2	1
9	Can be trusted	4	3	1	2	1
10	Respectful	4	3	1	2	1
No	Managerial Competence					
1	Leadership	4	3	-	2	-
2	Problem Solvers	4	3	-	2	-

360-Degree Feedback Design In Giving Feedback

The feedback-providing design in Era Ascot is based on the 360-Degree Feedback stages, which will produce a form of feedback. The feedback plan includes:

1.Determination of Research Objective

It is essential to know the performance of each employee from every position in a company. An employee performance evaluation is needed to find out the good and the bad of an employee's performance. The source of the evaluation obtained will be used as the basis for the development of each employee.

2.Determination of Assessment Instruments

The instrument that will be used in the *360-Degree Feedback* assessment in Era Ascot is based on the fundamental behavior of each employee. The behavior that will be used in this research is based on competence.

3.Source of Appraiser

Position	Rating Class			
	Self	Subordinate	Superior	Work colleague
Director	Director	Office Coordinator	Commissioner	Manager

		Team Leader		
		Marketing Associate		
Manager	Manager	Team Leader	director	Office Coordinator
		Marketing Associate		
Office Coordinator	Office Coordinator	-	director	Team Leader
			Manager	Marketing Associate
Team Leader	Team Leader	Marketing Associate	director	Office Coordinator
			Manager	Team Leader
Marketing Associate	Marketing Associate	-	director	Marketing Associate
			Manager	
			Team Leader	

4. Rating Scale

The rating scale used is the Likert scale, which is a scale used to measure attitudes and opinions and is generally used in filling out questionnaires. The following is the rating scale used:

Scale	Definition
1	Never displays behavior
2	Rarely displays behavior
3	Averagely displaying behavior
4	Reasonably consistent in displaying behavior
5	Always consistently displays behavior

5. 360-Degree Feedback Form

Below is the 360-Degree Feedback Form for the Team Leader Position:

Date started work :	
Assessment date:	
Name of Employee to be Assessed:	
Position of the Employee to be Assessed:	
Relationship with Employees to be Assessed:	

Core Competencies									
No	Competence	Level	Behavior Indicator	Code	Mark				
					1	2	3	4	5
1	Property Knowledge	2	Knowledge of property types and functions	KI-1					
			Building permits, and legal aspects	KI-2					

2	Home Funding Knowledge	2	Understand the types of home financing and how to use them	KI-3					
			Has the knowledge to maximize the funding function in conducting transactions.	KI-4					
3	Marketing Knowledge	2	Has the knowledge of how to market the property	KI-5					
			Knowledge of market analysis in property marketing	KI-6					
4	Communication	2	Able to create two-way communication	KI-7					
			Adjusting the way of communication with other parties	KI-8					
5	Relationship Management	2	Providing effective service and following up on customer needs	KI-9					
			Maintain good relationship with customers	KI-10					
6	Negotiation	2	Negotiate with property owners to get a listing	KI-11					
			Negotiation with potential customers to reach transactions	KI-12					
7	Technology Capability	2	Able to use system (computer, company application)	KI-13					
			Use of technology in team performance planning	KI-14					
8	Professional	2	Running a profession according to expertise	KI-15					
			Sense of responsibility towards the assigned team	KI-16					
9	Can be trusted	2	Be honest and trustworthy	KI-17					
			Responsible for giving directions and orders	KI-18					
10	Respectful	2	Behave with respect for everyone, customers and coworkers	KI-19					
			Appreciate every team member's performance and superior's decisions	KI-20					

Managerial Competence									
No	Competence	Level	Behavior Indicator	Code	Value				
					1	2	3	4	5
1	Leadership	2	Planning for team needs and time management	KM-1					
			Give directions and orders correctly	KM-2					
2	Problem Solver	2	Identification, collection of data and information related to problems	KM-3					
			Provide effective solutions to problems	KM-4					

6. Standard of assessment

After determining the performance form, the next step is to analyze data to create information, one of which is by using the 360-Degree Feedback method. This method compares the assessment results obtained from each rater classification. The following is a table of assessment interpretation results:

Mark	Definition of Value
1	Very bad
2	Bad
3	Enough
4	Good
5	Very good

Assessment Results from 360-Degree Feedback of Team Leader Core Competencies

Behavior Indicator	Average value			
	Self	Subordinate	Superior	Work colleague
KI-1	5	4.5	5	4.7
KI-2	4	4.6	4.5	4.7
KI-3	5	4.6	4	4.3
KI-4	5	4.6	5	5
KI-5	5	4.5	4.5	4.3
KI-6	4	4.2	5	5
KI-7	5	4.8	5	5
KI-8	3	4.3	4.5	4.7
KI-9	4	4.5	5	5
KI-10	5	4.5	5	5
KI-11	5	4.4	4.5	4.7
KI-12	5	4.8	5	5
KI-13	5	4.3	5	5
KI-14	4	4.4	4	4.3
KI-15	5	4.4	5	5
KI-16	4	4.6	5	5
KI-17	3	5.0	4.5	4.7
KI-18	4	5.0	5	5
KI-19	5	4.8	5	5

KI-20	5	5.0	5	5
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Calculation Explanation:

Formula :

$$\bar{X} = \frac{\sum_1^5 ni \cdot xi}{\sum_1^5 ni}$$

\bar{X}	= Average Score
i	= rating scale (1-5)
n	= number of raters
x	= the value of the rating scale

360 Degree Feedback Performance Assessment of Core Competence Recaptulation

Employee Name :

Position : Team Leader

Behavior Indicator	Average Score			
	Self	Subordinate	Superior	Peers
KI-1	5	4,5	5	4,7
KI-2	4	4,6	4,5	4,7
KI-3	5	4,6	4	4,3
KI-4	5	4,6	5	5
KI-5	5	4,5	4,5	4,3
KI-6	4	4,2	5	5
KI-7	5	4,8	5	5
KI-8	3	4,3	4,5	4,7
KI-9	4	4,5	5	5
KI-10	5	4,5	5	5
KI-11	5	4,4	4,5	4,7
KI-12	5	4,8	5	5
KI-13	5	4,3	5	5
KI-14	4	4,4	4	4,3
KI-15	5	4,4	5	5
KI-16	4	4,6	5	5
KI-17	3	5,0	4,5	4,7
KI-18	4	5,0	5	5
KI-19	5	4,8	5	5
KI-20	5	5,0	5	5

7. Feedback

There are three methods of giving feedback that the company can use, including: i) Self-study; ii) Group sessions, and; iii) One-on-one session

8. Feedback period

In order to ensure feedback can be provided effectively, then assessments and feedback should correspond with the employee contract period, which is once every six months. This is so that the performance of company employees can be adequately controlled.

Pros and Cons of 360-Degree Feedback

360-degree feedback was designed to help Era Ascot collect performance appraisal data so that it can provide objective feedback. The following describes the advantages and disadvantages of 360-degree feedback (Amstrong, 2006, pp. 164-165).

Advantages of 360-Degree Feedback:

1. For Organizations or Companies

- Strengthen the desired business competencies through superior competency classification of each employee
- Clarify critical aspects of employee performance
- Identify the strengths used for business advantage, namely the excellent performances of its employees
- More valid and objective feedback perception

2. For Employees

- Gaining a broader perspective on performance as well as evaluation material
- Increase awareness and relevance of competence
- Assist and direct the development of each employee (management level)
- Encourage more honest and open feedback

Disadvantages of 360-Degree Feedback:

- Due to data collected from various sources, data processing will be more difficult if done manually.
- Employees who are not ready to accept negative feedback will become stressed, resulting in decreased performance
- Some companies do not take further action after providing feedback to employees

Conclusion

The proposed design of the 360-degree feedback in providing feedback during the Ascot Era can be implemented for all employees. Assessment using the 360-degree feedback method is carried out based on

competence. Competencies consist of core competencies and managerial competencies. The assessment process is carried out by collecting assessments from multiple sources. Assessors in this process can be classified into four classifications: self, superiors, subordinates, and coworkers. The multi-source assessment is carried out to help employees compare the assessment of a competency assessed by themselves with the assessment of other employees. The assessment result will be presented in a table with each competency's value, a comparison graph of the average value of each rating classification, and a graph of the average value of the overall competency. The 360-degree feedback method has both advantages and disadvantages. The advantages for the company are; strengthen the desired business competencies, identify strengths that can be used for business advantages, identify strengths that can be used for business benefits, and perceive more valid and objective feedback. The advantages for employees are; individuals gain a broader perspective on performance, increase awareness and relevance of competencies, assist employees at the management level in directing each employee's development, and encourage honest feedback. While the disadvantages of 360-degree feedback are; Data processing done manually will be more difficult, employees who are not ready to receive negative feedback will become stressed, and the company will not take further action after providing feedback to employees.

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